

DYNAMIC RESPONSE OF A LAMINATED COMPOSITE PLATE WITH INTERFACE LAYERS

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ABSTRACT

A model study of dynamic interface stresses in a laminated composite plate in the presence of adhesive interface layers is presented in this paper. Since the performance and service life of laminated composites are critically dependent on the integrity of the bond, the objective of this study is to analyze the effect of bond properties on the normal and shear stresses at the interfaces. Results are presented showing the changes in the dynamic stresses when different models for the bond layers are used.

Key words: guided waves, spring model, interface layer, dynamic response, delamination.

1. INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are widely used in many industries now. Usually, they are fabricated as laminated structures, where two adjacent laminae are bonded by a layer of adhesive material. Frequently, the failure of the whole structure is initiated from the failure of the weak interface layers. For this reason the strength of interface layers and its effects on the dynamic response of laminated structures have been a focus of attention from researchers interested in nondestructive evaluation of bond properties and failure of composite structures. Several studies have been reported on this topic. A comprehensive review of the literature can be found in a recent special issue of the Journal of Nondestructive Evaluation [1]. Various interface models have been used in order to simplify the dynamic analysis. Among the most commonly used models is the spring model in which the jumps in the displacements at the interface are assumed to be proportional to the traction components, which are taken to be continuous across the interface. In our earlier studies [2 - 4] it has been shown that predictions of the dispersion behavior and dynamic surface displacements when a spring model is used can be vastly different than the exact model calculations for the imperfect interface. In this paper we present a model study of the effect of interface layers on the dynamic stresses at the interfaces in a five-layer composite plate.

2. FORMULATION

2.1 Green's functions: exact model

We consider a laminated composite plate containing N layers. Its geometry is shown in Figure 1. Each layer is assumed to be homogeneous and transversely isotropic.

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A transversely isotropic material has five independent elastic stiffnesses, namely, C_{11} , C_{33} , C_{12} , C_{13} and C_{55} . The definition of these elastic constants can be found in many textbooks (see, for example, Green and Zerna [5]). All deformations are assumed to be small so that the problem can be analyzed using linear elastodynamic theories. The layers are assumed to be perfectly bonded to one another, so that the displacement and stress vectors are continuous across the interfaces. It will be assumed that the Cartesian coordinates axes x , y , z , are parallel to the principal axes of each lamina. We will consider a two-dimensional (plane strain) problem. The Green's functions for a given medium $G_{ki}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')$ are defined as the displacements in the i^{th} direction produced at a field point \mathbf{x} , usually called "receiver", due to a unit impulsive load in the k^{th} direction applied at a point \mathbf{x}' , called "source". As shown in Figure 1, a uniform unit line source along the y axis at a point (x', z') is applied to this laminated composite plate. We consider the plate shown in Figure 1 as a crossply composite plate, the fiber direction in each ply being along either x or y axis. Thus, the x - z (or, y - z) plane is a plane of symmetry and the problem can be modeled as two dimensional. Then the equations of motion are,

$$C_{11}\hat{u}_{xx} + (C_{13} + C_{55})\hat{w}_{zz} + C_{55}\hat{u}_{zz} = \rho\hat{u}_{tt} \quad (1a)$$

$$C_{33}\hat{w}_{zz} + (C_{13} + C_{55})\hat{u}_{xz} + C_{55}\hat{w}_{xz} = \rho\hat{w}_{tt} \quad (1b)$$

where ρ is the mass density and it is assumed that the wave propagation is in the x - z plane. $\hat{u}(t, x, z)$ and $\hat{w}(t, x, z)$ are displacements in the x and z directions, respectively. The subscripts denote the derivatives of these displacements with respect to space variables (x and z) and time (t). We will define the Fourier transform of a dependent variable $\hat{\phi}(t, x, z)$ as,

$$\phi(\omega, k, z) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \hat{\phi}(t, x, z) e^{-i(\omega t - kx)} dt dx$$

Taking then the Fourier transforms of Equations (1) we obtain

$$C_{55}u_{zz} + (C_{13} + C_{55})(ik)w_z + (\rho\omega^2 - C_{11}k^2)u = 0 \quad (2a)$$

$$C_{33}w_{zz} + (C_{13} + C_{55})(ik)u_z + (\rho\omega^2 - C_{55}k^2)w = 0 \quad (2b)$$

where ω and k are the Fourier transform variables in t and x , respectively. The expressions for the displacements at the m^{th} layer that satisfy the above equations are (see Datta *et al.* [3]);

Figure 1. Geometry of a laminated plate

$$u = A_1 e^{is_1(z-z_{m-1})} + A_2 e^{is_2(z-z_{m-1})} + A_3 e^{is_1(z_m-z)} + A_4 e^{is_2(z_m-z)} \quad (3a)$$

$$w = r_1 A_1 e^{is_1(z-z_{m-1})} + r_2 A_2 e^{is_2(z-z_{m-1})} - r_1 A_3 e^{is_1(z_m-z)} - r_2 A_4 e^{is_2(z_m-z)} \quad (3b)$$

$u(\omega, k, z)$ and $w(\omega, k, z)$ can be interpreted as displacement components in x and z directions at a specific frequency ω and a wavenumber k . The constants, A's, are coefficients which are as yet undetermined. The m^{th} layer is bounded by the coordinates z_{m-1} and z_m , where z is the vertical coordinate of the receiver in this layer. Furthermore, for the m^{th} layer, other relevant parameters are defined as,

$$s_{1,2}^2 = \frac{1}{2\beta} [k_2^2(\beta + 1) + (\delta^2 - 1 - \alpha\beta)k^2] \pm \frac{1}{2\beta} \sqrt{[(\beta + 1)k_2^2 - \gamma k^2]^2 - 4\beta(k_2^2 - \alpha k^2)(k_2^2 - k^2)} \quad (4)$$

$$\alpha = \frac{C_{11}}{C_{55}}, \quad \beta = \frac{C_{33}}{C_{55}}, \quad k_2 = \frac{\omega}{\sqrt{C_{55}/\rho}}$$

$$\delta = 1 + \frac{C_{13}}{C_{55}}, \quad \gamma = 1 + \alpha\beta - \delta^2$$

$$r_{1,2} = \frac{C_{55}k_2^2 - C_{55}s_{1,2}^2 - C_{11}k^2}{(C_{13} + C_{55})ks_{1,2}} \quad (5)$$

The corresponding traction components on the surface $z = \text{constant}$ are

$$\sigma_{zz} = P_1 A_1 e^{is_1(z-z_{m-1})} + P_2 A_2 e^{is_2(z-z_{m-1})} + P_1 A_3 e^{is_1(z_m-z)} + P_2 A_4 e^{is_2(z_m-z)} \quad (6a)$$

$$\sigma_{zx} = Q_1 A_1 e^{is_1(z-z_{m-1})} + Q_2 A_2 e^{is_2(z-z_{m-1})} - Q_1 A_3 e^{is_1(z_m-z)} - Q_2 A_4 e^{is_2(z_m-z)} \quad (6b)$$

where

$$P_{1,2} = i(C_{33}r_{1,2}s_{1,2} + C_{13}k)$$

$$Q_{1,2} = iC_{55}(kr_{1,2} + s_{1,2})$$

So, in matrix form, the displacement-stress vector can be expressed as

$$Q(m)E(z, m)A(m) = T(z) \quad m = 1, 2, \dots, N. \quad (7)$$

In Equation (7)

$$Q(m) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ r_1 & r_2 & -r_1 & -r_2 \\ P_1 & P_2 & P_1 & P_2 \\ Q_1 & Q_2 & -Q_1 & -Q_2 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$E(z, m) = \text{diag}(e^{is_1(z-z_{m-1})}, e^{is_2(z-z_{m-1})}, e^{is_1(z_m-z)}, e^{is_2(z_m-z)})$$

$$A(m) = \{A_1 \ A_2 \ A_3 \ A_4\}^T$$

$$T(z) = \{u \ w \ \sigma_{zz} \ \sigma_{zx}\}^T$$

where the superscript T denotes transpose. T(z) is the displacement-stress vector.

It may be noted that the first two terms in $E(z,m)$ represent waves propagating along the positive z -axis, while the last two along the negative z -axis. Besides, the elements of $E(z,m)$ are bounded for all k and decay exponentially for large k .

We define the m^{th} interface as the surface between layers m and $m+1$. So, the interfacial values of $T(z_m)$ are

$$T(z_m^+) = Q(m+1)E(z_m^+, m+1)A(m+1)$$

$$T(z_m^-) = Q(m)E(z_m^-, m)A(m)$$

According to the definition of $E(z,m)$, we have

$$E(z_m^+) = \text{Diag} [1 \quad 1 \quad e_1(m+1) \quad e_2(m+1)]$$

$$E(z_m^-) = \text{Diag} [e_1(m) \quad e_2(m) \quad 1 \quad 1]$$

where we have written for convenience

$$e_{1,2}(m) = e^{i s_{1,2} h(m)}$$

Here $h(m)$ is the thickness of layer m .

In order to obtain the interface conditions in a convenient form, the notation $T(z_m)_\pm^+$ is used to denote the jump discontinuity in $T(z)$ across the interface $z = z_m$ from its negative to positive side. Thus the m^{th} interface condition can be written as

$$Q(m)E(z_m^-, m)A(m) - Q(m+1)E(z_m^+, m+1)A(m+1) = T(z_m)_\pm^+ \quad (8)$$

where $m=1,2,\dots,N-1$, and

$$T(z_m)_\pm^+ = \{0 \quad 0 \quad \sigma_{zz}(z_m^-) - \sigma_{zz}(z_m^+) \quad \sigma_{xz}(z_m^-) - \sigma_{xz}(z_m^+)\} \quad (9)$$

The first two zeros represent the fact that the displacements are continuous at the m^{th} interface.

The stress boundary conditions at the top and bottom surfaces are

$$T(0^+) = \{ \sigma_{zz}(z=0) \quad \sigma_{xz}(z=0) \} \quad (10)$$

$$T(z_N^-) = \{ \sigma_{zz}(z=H) \quad \sigma_{xz}(z=H) \} \quad (11)$$

where H is the total thickness of the plate. If there are no loads applied to these surfaces, then the entries in these two equations are all zero. If an impulsive load is applied at one of these surfaces, then there will be a jump in one of the stress components, σ_{zz} , σ_{xz} , depending on the direction of the applied load.

By using equations (8) - (11), the local matrices then can be linked together to form a global matrix. This global matrix equation will provide $4N$ equations for the $4N$ unknown A 's, which then can be solved. Once these unknowns are known, we can then determine the Fourier transforms of the displacements and stresses at any location in the plate. After taking the inverse transform the physical quantities of interest due to an impulsive load can be written in the form of a double integral over the frequency and the wave number spaces, as,

$$\hat{g}(t, x, z) = \frac{1}{4\pi^2} \int_0^\infty \int_{-\infty}^\infty g(\omega, k, z) e^{-i(\omega t - kx)} dk d\omega \quad (12)$$

The integrand has poles on the real k -axis for any given ω . It also has imaginary and complex poles. In order to carry out the k -integration along the real k -axis a small dissipation in the material is assumed. After the k -integration has been performed, the representation in

time domain is then carried out by taking inverse fast Fourier transformation (FFT) with respect to ω .

It may be noted here that the isotropic case can also be investigated as a special case. Similarly, if the thickness of the bottom layer (h_N) is very large compared to other layers, then the model can easily be used for layers on top of a homogeneous half-space.

2.2 Green's functions: spring model

Next, we extend the previous derivation of Green's functions to the case of the spring model. Assume that the thickness of the interface layer is h_0 and its elastic stiffnesses are λ_0 and μ_0 . The thickness of the layer is assumed much smaller than the wave length as well as other characteristic lengths in this plate. Thus the stresses in the interface layer can be considered as uniform and can be formulated as

$$\sigma_{zx} = \left(\frac{u^+ - u^-}{h_0} \right) \mu_0, \quad \sigma_{zz} = \left(\frac{w^+ - w^-}{h_0} \right) (\lambda_0 + 2\mu_0) \quad (13)$$

Since the stresses are continuous, the interface condition now becomes

$$BQ(m)E(z_m^-, m)A(m) - Q(m+1)E(z_m^+, m+1)A(m+1) = T(z_m)^+ \quad (14)$$

where matrix B is defined as, according to Equation (13),

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & \frac{h_0}{\mu_0} \\ 0 & 1 & \frac{h_0}{\lambda_0 + 2\mu_0} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Thus the derivation of the Green's functions are only changed slightly. Two extreme cases can be easily identified from the equations above. First, when the off diagonal terms are very small, matrix B approaches the identity matrix I and Equation (14) represents a perfect bond (Equation(8)). If the off diagonal terms have very large values and the displacements are to be finite, then according to Equation (13), the associated stresses should vanish. This would represent a delamination.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

The present study is focused on the graphite/epoxy laminated plate with interface bond layers. We will consider a $[0^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]$ crossply plate. The thickness and material properties of each lamina and the interface layer are given in Table 1. The total thickness of the plate is 5.08mm. The impact response when a line vertical force is assumed to act in the z-direction on one free surface of the plate ($z = 0$) will be studied. The x-axis is chosen to be parallel to the fiber direction in the topmost ply. Two different models will be used to study the guided wave propagation in the laminated composite plate. They are: the exact model with interface layers and and the spring model. In this paper, we will focus our attention on the comparison of the spring model predictions with those of the exact model for the interface layers.

The time dependence of the line load is taken to be a sine pulse of duration τ in the form,

$$f(t) = \sin\left(\frac{2\pi t}{\tau}\right)$$

Two different time durations were considered: $\tau = 2.3\mu s$ (a short pulse) and $\tau = 10\mu s$ (a long pulse). Figure 2 shows the normal stress, σ_{zz} , at the intersections of the z-axis with the top and bottom interfaces (nodes 1,2, and 3, 4) of the two adhesive layers.

This may be compared with the results for the spring model shown in Figure 3. These are for the long pulse duration. It may be noted that in the spring model the traction components are assumed to be the same at the top and bottom interfaces of the adhesive layers. It can be seen from Figure 2 that the normal stresses are almost the same at the adjacent nodes, although there are phase differences. Figures 2 and 3 show that both models predict nearly identical results. It was found that this was true for the short pulse also (not shown here). For the short pulse the peak amplitude was found to be 50 percent larger, however. Figures 4 and 5 show the behavior when the elastic moduli of the bond layers are 10^{-3} times the original values. These are for the exact and spring models, respectively. It can be seen that there are significant differences in the two results. For the short pulse these differences are exacerbated(not shown here).

Table 1. Material properties and thickness

Material	$\rho(\text{g/cm}^3)$	$c_{11}(\text{GPa})$	$c_{33}(\text{GPa})$	$c_{55}(\text{GPa})$	$c_{13}(\text{GPa})$	Thickness(mm)
Gr/Ep(0)	1.8	160.72	13.92	7.07	6.42	1.5875
Gr/Ep(90)	1.8	13.92	13.92	3.50	6.92	1.5875
Bond	1.2	8.65	8.65	1.95	4.75	0.15875

Figure 2. σ_{zz} at the intersections of the z-axis (exact model)

Figure 3. σ_{zz} at the intersections of the z -axis (spring model)

Figure 4. σ_{zz} at the intersections of the z -axis (exact model) when the bond layers are 10^{-3} times

Figure 5. σ_{zz} at the intersections of the z-axis (spring model) when the bond layers are 10^{-3} times

4. CONCLUSIONS

The effect of the interface layers on the dynamic response of a laminated composite plate has been studied by the exact and an approximate model (spring) for the interface layers. Numerical results for the dynamic stresses at the interface when the plate is subjected to an impact load have been presented to show that the two model predictions can be quite different when the bond stiffnesses are low. The spring model has been found to provide good approximation to the exact model at low frequencies.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The work reported here was supported in part by a grant from the Office of Naval Research (# N00014-92-J-1346). Financial support for the first author provided by the University of Connecticut is gratefully acknowledged.

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